

III. International Mediterranean Forest and Environment Symposium

COMPARISON OF ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY CHEMICALS USED IN BLEACHING OF WASTE NEWSPAPERS

Mustafa Çiçekler¹ Ayşe Özdemir¹ and Ahmet Tutuş¹*

¹Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi, Orman Endüstri Mühendisliği Bölümü, Kahramanmaraş, Türkiye

*Corresponding author: mcicekler87@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this study, the effects of environmentally friendly chemicals used in waste newspapers bleaching on optical and physical properties were investigated. The waste newspaper pulps obtained after pulping process were deinked with using flotation method and subjected to bleaching processes. As environmentally friendly chemicals, formamidine sulphinic acid (0.5%, 1%, 1.5%), sodium dithionite (0.5%, 1%, 1.5%) and hydrogen peroxide (3%, 5%, 7%) were used in bleaching processes. The results showed that the optical properties of pulps bleached with sodium dithionite and formamidine sulphinic acid (FAS) were significantly better than that of hydrogen peroxide. The breaking length and burst index of pulps bleached with hydrogen peroxide were higher than that of other chemicals. The pulps bleached with FAS was better in terms of both physical and optical properties than that of sodium dithionite. In short, FAS used as bleaching agent produced less costly pulp with better physical and optical paper properties.

Keywords: Bleaching, dithionite, FAS, peroxide, waste newspaper.

1. INTRODUCTION

Newspaper paper is a low-cost, non-archived, mainly composed of wood pulp and used mainly for printing newspapers and other publications and advertising materials. It was invented by Charles Fenerty in Nova Scotia, Canada in 1844, and is usually grayish in color and has a distinctive texture. It is generally used in printing presses (offset, flexographic and letterpress) in the long paper network and is not preferred to be used as individual paper (Burger, 2007; Pesman, 2010). Newspapers are preferred by publishers and printers because they meet their typical needs in terms of their low price, their strength and their ability to accept four-color printing. Newspaper pulp is usually produced with mechanical pulps. Lignin is not removed in the pulp produced without any chemical treatment. The paper becomes brittle and yellowish as a result of its interaction with the sun or air. The main reason for this is the high amount of lignin it contains. Generally, the raw materials used in the production of newsprint are various coniferous trees (mostly spruce, fir and pine). Recently, newspaper production worldwide is made from recycled fibers (Lee, et al., 2011; Desai & Iyer, 2016). In recent years, newsprint is not produced in Turkey and all newsprints are imported from another country. Table 1 shows the amounts of newsprint produced and consumed in Turkey and world (FAO, 2019).

Table 1. The production and consumption amounts of newsprint in Turkey and world

Years	World		Turkey	
	Production (thousand tons)	Consumption (thousand tons)	Production (thousand tons)	Consumption (thousand tons)
2012	30.509	30.338	-	454
2013	28.959	28.743	-	433
2014	26.963	26.859	-	391
2015	24.859	24.855	-	347
2016	23.975	23.956	-	262
2017	22.199	22.525	-	224
2018	20.479	20.833	-	222

When Table 1 is examined, newsprint consumption in Turkey and world is steadily decreasing. The advancement of technology and the increase in digitalization all over the world cause these decreases. Moreover, the same table shows the newsprint is not produced in Turkey. Because pulp is produced from only waste papers in Turkey and is evaluated in the corrugated cardboard industry.

In terms of providing economy especially in bleaching processes, both the costs of chemicals and yield of the pulp obtained after the bleaching process are of great importance. While some of the chemicals used have a significant effect on yield, some have little effect on yield. Chemicals that provide the least contribution on the yield can only whiten their color without destroying the lignin and other coloring agents in the pulp during the bleaching process. These methods are generally considered in the production of coated paper and newsprint. It is desirable to have high yields in production of these paper types (Bostanci, 1987; Smook, 1989). Because of consumer awareness and some legal regulations, the use of environmentally friendly chemicals in bleaching processes has increased. Hydrogen peroxide, dithionite, formamidine sulphinic acid (FAS), oxygen, ozone and peroxy acids used in bleaching waste paper are expressed as environmentally friendly bleaching chemicals (Bajpai, 2012).

Hydrogen peroxide is a chemical that has the advantage of being compatible with the environment due to its decomposition into water and oxygen (Bajpai, 2012). Sodium dithionite, known as sodium hydrosulfite is a reductive bleaching agent. Reductive bleaching is important not only for bleaching, but also for removing color from colored recycled paper and carbonless paper (Dumont et al., 1994; Hache et al., 1994; Fluet & Shepperd, 1997; Bajpai, 2012). FAS is a low odor, crystalline reducing agent and can be used on all types of waste paper bleaching. It is particularly recommended for use when using furnish that contains colored paper. Its use as a bleaching agent was first suggested in the textile industry (Kronis, 1996). The aim of this study is to determine the effects of hydrogen peroxide, dithionite and FAS chemicals used in bleaching waste newspaper papers and to compare them with each other.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

National newspaper wastes dated 04 November 2014 were used in the study. All the newspapers used were of the same date and care was taken to ensure that the transactions made were not outside the standard. Recycling of waste newspapers was carried out in four stages; pulping, storage, de-inking and bleaching.

Waste newspapers were cut into pieces of 2x2 cm by hand according to the International Association of the Deinking Industry (INGEDE) (Method 11p –5.5) and put into polyethylene bags and stored protected from light and temperature. The waste newspapers were converted into pulp in the Hobart type pulping apparatus under the conditions given in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Conditions for pulping waste newspaper

Pulping Conditions	Revolution (level)	Cons. (%)	Time (min)
Pre-wetting	-	10	10
Pulping	1-2	10	22

In the pulping process, 0.6% sodium hydroxide (NaOH), 0.7% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), 1.8% sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃) and 0.8% oleic acid were used. The waste pulp taken from the Hobart was stored in a water bath for 60 minutes at 45 °C at 5% concentration. At the end of the indicated time, the pulps were transferred to the flotation unit to remove the inks. Degussa type flotation cell was used for the deinking process and flotation conditions were given in Table 3.

Table 3. Flotation conditions for waste newspaper pulps

Flotation Conditions	
Concentration	%0.8-1
Temperature	45 °C
Time	30 min
Mixing speed	1450 rpm
Water hardness	160 ppm
Air flow	2.5 lt/min

The froth accumulated on the surface during the deinking process was removed with the help of a scraper. After flotation, water was removed from the deinked pulps to 25-30% solids. Table 4 indicates the bleaching conditions applied to the deinked pulps.

Table 4. The bleaching conditions for the deinked pulps

Bleaching Conditions	H ₂ O ₂	FAS	Dithionite
Charge (%)	3, 5, 7	0.5, 1.0, 1.5	0.5, 1.0, 1.5
Cons. (%)	12	5	5
Temp. (°C)	75	75	65
Time (min)	60	60	60
EDTA (%)	0.5	-	0.2
MgSO ₄ (%)	0.5	-	-
Na ₂ SiO ₃ (%)	2	-	-
NaOH (%)	H ₂ O ₂ /0.75	FAS/2	-

Bleaching processes were carried out in a shaking water bath and the pulps were bleached in polyethylene bags in the water bath.

The bleached pulps were beaten to 50 ± 5 SR° freeness level by Hollander Beater. Then, test papers with 50 ± 2 (g.m⁻²) grammages were produced using a Rapid Kothén sheet former according to ISO 5269-2:2004. The newspapers were conditioned at 23 ± 1 °C and $65 \pm 1\%$ relative humidity in a conditioning room. All tests of the produced boards were carried out according to ISO, ASTM and TAPPI test methods and the gray boards were subjected to the tests specified in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Optical, physical tests and standards applied to newspapers

Physical and Optical Tests	Standards
Breaking length	TAPPI T494 om-01
Burst index	TAPPI T403 om-15
ERIC	ISO 22754
Brightness	ISO 2469:2014
Whiteness	ISO 2469:2014
Yellowness	ASTM E313

SPSS was used to determine the effect on the physical and optical properties of newspapers bleached with H₂O₂, FAS, and dithionite. Test results were determined by one-way analysis of variance and Duncan's test for 95% confidence interval ($P < 0.05$). Duncan's test was applied in case of differences between the groups by statistical analysis of variance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some physical and optical properties of the pulps bleached with different chemicals and conditions were summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Some physical and optical properties of newspapers bleached with different condition

Bleaching Conditions	Bleaching Yield (%)	Whiteness (ISO%)	Brightness (ISO%)	Yellowness (ISO%)	ERIC (ppm)	Breaking Length (km)	Burst Index (kPa.m ² /g)
Control	-	47.15b	41.40c	16.38a	894b	3.94a	2.33a
0.5% FAS	66.99	56.66a	48.19b	20.59c	344a	3.05b	1.50b
1.0% FAS	66.12	57.33a	49.67a	18.37b	343a	3.14b	1.69b
1.5% FAS	65.25	57.24a	49.68a	18.20b	335a	3.08b	1.63b
Control	-	47.15d	41.40a	16.38a	894c	3.94a	2.33a
3% H ₂ O ₂	71.28	55.01c	38.13b	39.87b	314b	3.57a	2.10b
5% H ₂ O ₂	66.04	56.24b	36.34c	45.66c	273a	3.85a	2.25a
7% H ₂ O ₂	65.88	57.25a	37.98b	43.50d	260a	3.68a	2.16a
Control	-	47.15c	41.40c	16.38a	894b	3.94a	2.33a
0.5% Dithionite	66.86	57.62b	48.99b	20.05b	329a	3.36a	1.82c
1.0% Dithionite	66.57	58.52a	50.14a	19.04c	342a	3.36a	1.85c
1.5% Dithionite	66.82	58.73a	50.71a	18.13d	340a	3.52a	2.08b

*Mean values with the same lower-case letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's mean separation test.

According to statistical analyzes, the optimum bleaching conditions for FAS, H₂O₂, and dithionite were determined as 1.0%, 7%, and 1.5%, respectively. The chemicals used for bleaching of waste newspaper were compared based on these conditions. The ERIC values of the pulps bleached with the chemicals decreased significantly. When bleaching yields were examined, it was observed that there was no significant difference between the chemicals used bleaching processes. The effects of the bleaching chemicals on the some optical properties of the pulps were indicated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Effects of the bleaching chemicals on some optical properties

All chemicals improved the whiteness values of the pulps and the highest value (58.7 ISO%) were obtained with using dithionite. Dithionite and FAS are especially essential for eliminating color from waste newspaper pulps. It is stated that FAS and dithionite are the primary bleaching agent for the bleaching of dye compounds in the pulp (Vincent et al., 1997). The whiteness values increase with the removal of dyes causing darkness in pulps (Kronis, 1996; Meyers et al., 1999). While the brightness values improved by the bleaching chemicals as well as the whiteness values, the best result for brightness was observed in pulps bleached with dithionite. Contrary to whiteness and brightness values, yellowness values were negatively affected by bleaching processes. In particular, the yellowness values of the pulp bleached with hydrogen peroxide increased more than the pulps bleached with other chemicals. Because of high lignin content, hydrogen peroxide dissolved a part of lignin and re-precipitated it as colored chromophore groups on the pulp and negatively affected both brightness and yellowness values of the newspaper (Tutus & Usta, 2004; Cicekler & Tutus, 2019).

Effects of the bleaching chemicals used in this study on breaking lengths and burst indices of pulps bleached with optimum conditions were presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Effects of the bleaching chemicals on some physical properties

After the bleaching processes, the physical properties of the papers decreased. The chemicals used in the bleaching process applied to pulps to remove or discolor lignin affect carbohydrates as well as lignin. Therefore, bleaching chemicals degrade carbohydrates as well as reaction with lignin (Kirici et al., 2003; Dence & Reeve, 2013). Due to these degradations in the cellulose chains, the physical properties are adversely affected. Pulps bleached with peroxide and dithionite have better physical properties than pulps bleached with FAS. Pulps bleached with peroxide gave the best results on physical properties. Peroxide bleaching has the potential of enhancing fiber-fiber bonding by enhancing carboxylic acid group on fibers.

4. CONCLUSION

According to the statistical analysis, optimum results were obtained by using 1% FAS, 7% H₂O₂ and 1.5% dithionite for bleaching waste newspaper pulps. All of the environmentally friendly chemicals used in waste newspaper pulps bleaching have a positive effect on the whiteness values, while the peroxide has reduced the brightness values. Bleaching chemicals increased

the yellowness values of waste newspaper pulps. All bleaching agents adversely affected physical properties, whereas peroxide showed the least effect. Peroxide was more effective on ERIC than other bleaching chemicals. When the costs of bleaching chemicals used in optimum conditions were calculated, it was found that FAS was more economical than other chemicals. An environmentally friendly and economical bleaching process can be achieved by using these chemicals in one or more stages for bleaching waste newspapers and other waste papers.

5. REFERENCES

- Bajpai, P., 2012. Environmentally benign approaches for pulp bleaching: Second edition. In *Environmentally Benign Approaches for Pulp Bleaching: Second Edition*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-51724-1.X5000-X>
- Bostanci, S., 1987. *Pulp Production and Bleaching Technology*. Tabzon/Turkey: Forestry Faculty, Publication No. 114/13.
- Burger, P., 2007. *Charles Fenerty and his paper invention*. Canada: PB Publishing.
- Cicekler, M., & Tutus, A., 2019. A research on recycling of waste newspapers. *International Congress on Agriculture and Forestry Research (AGRIFOR)*, 125–135. Muğla-Turkey.
- Dence, C. W., & Reeve, D. W., 2013. Pulp Bleaching: Principles and Practices. In *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- Desai, D. I., & Iyer, B. D., 2016. Biodeinking of old newspaper pulp using a cellulase-free xylanase preparation of *Aspergillus niger* DX-23. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*, 5, 78–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcab.2015.11.001>
- Dumont, I., Fluet, A., Giasson, J., & Shepperd, P., 1994. *Pulp Paper Can.*, 95(2), 136.
- FAO, 2019. The Food and Agriculture Organization. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FO>
- Fluet, A., & Shepperd, P., 1997. *Progress in Paper Recycling*.
- Hache, M. J. A., Brungart, J. R., Munroe, D. C., & Teodorescu, G., 1994. *Pulp Paper Can.*, 95(2), 120.
- Kirci, H., Pesman, E., & Kalyoncu, E. E., 2003. Sodium Perborate Monohydrate Reinforced Oxygen Delignification Stage of Kraft Pulps. II. *International Symposium on Boron*, 339–343. Eskişehir-Turkey.
- Kronis, J. D., 1996. Optimum conditions play major role in recycled fiber bleaching with FAS. *Pulp and Paper*, 70(9), 113–117.
- Lee, C. K., Ibrahim, D., Ibrahim, C. O., & Rosli, W. D. W., 2011. Enzymatic and chemical deinking of mixed office wastepaper and old newspaper: Paper quality and effluent characteristics. *BioResources*, 6(4), 3859–3875. <https://doi.org/10.15376/biores.6.4.3859-3875>
- Meyers, P., Wang, D., & Hache, M. (1999). DBI, a novel bleaching process for recycled fibres. IN: *Tappi 99-Preparing for the Next Millenium*, 373. Atlanta, GA, USA.
- Pesman, E., 2010. *Determination of ink removal and bleaching properties of old news and magazine papers*. Doctoral Thesis, Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences, Karadeniz Technical University.
- Smook, G. A., 1989. *Handbook for Pulp and Paper Technologists*. Angus Wilde Publ.
- Tutus, A., & Usta, M., 2004. Bleaching of chemithermomechanical pulp (CTMP) using environmentally friendly chemicals. *Journal of Environmental Biology*, 25(2), 141–145.
- Vincent, A. H. D., Khong, C., & Rizzon, E., 1997. FAS (thiourea dioxide) bleaching of recycled pulp. *Appita Journal*, 50(5), 393–399.